

PERMISSIBLE LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DEFECTS IN ORGANIC 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to study and predict low velocity / low energy impact defects in 3D woven composites. Impact tests at different energy levels were performed and analysed using microscopic observations in order to understand damage mechanisms occurring in these materials. Finite element simulations were performed using the continuum damage model ODM_PMC developed at Onera for woven composites under static loadings. A two-step simulation approach has been proposed to predict both the damage distribution induced by impact and then, the residual performance. Encouraging results have been obtained and the capability of the modelling approach by comparison with experimental results has been demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to reduce the weight of aircrafts, composite materials are increasingly being used on primary structures. One major concern in the aerospace industry with composites is that the material can easily be damaged through impact events such as hail, bird strike, runway debris, and dropped tools. The impact resistance of unidirectional laminate composites has been widely studied for many years. Experimental studies have shown that a low velocity impact causes matrix cracking, fibres fracture and delamination between plies [1]. Due to delamination, an important loss of the residual strength under compressive loading is observed for such materials. The strength of laminate structures under compressive loading is mainly studied through an experimental point of view which requires a lot of tests. It can also be predicted by using a simplified representation of impact damage (hole, single delamination, etc.) but still, a lot of experimental data is needed in order to calibrate the models. A more predictable solution consists in an accurate estimation of the impact damages with simulations and then, the use of the results to simulate the post-impact compressive loading with the same model. Very few authors [2, 3] succeeded in proceeding this way, mainly because of numeric difficulties to take into account delamination into impact simulations.

Because of the poor impact resistance of unidirectional laminate composites, 3D woven composites are planned to be used in structures exposed to impact and the main advantage of 3D woven composites is that large delaminations are prevented thanks to yarns linking the layers together. Few studies can be found on impact damage resistance of recent 3D woven composites. The influence of the reinforcement architecture on impact and post-impact behaviour has been studied in [4, 5]. It has been pointed out that the CAI (Compression After Impact) strength is improved by using three dimensional woven composites instead of unidirectional or 2D laminates. Damage mechanisms in 3D woven composites are very different from those encountered in laminates. Since large delaminations do not appear in 3D woven composites, CAI test may not be the only loading that has to be studied [6]. Some recent experimental studies [6, 7] show that low velocity impacts on 3D woven composite create debondings between the different layers; matrix cracking and few fibres bundle fracture. Only

few impact modelling studies [7] can be found in the literature but the agreement with experimental data remains limited because of the complexity of the damage mechanisms.

This study aims to propose a modelling strategy to predict low velocity / low energy impact damage and the residual strength of polymer matrix 3D woven composites, which meets the design office requirements. The first step has consisted in understanding the damage mechanisms that appear under impact by performing impact tests. Then, the Onera Damage Model (ODM), developed for 3D woven composites structures under static loading defined at the macroscopic scale, has been used in finite element simulations for impact solicitations and residual strength predictions.

2 DAMAGE MECHANISMS UNDER IMPACT IN 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

2.1 Experimental device

A falling weight impact testing system as illustrated on Figure 1 has been used to perform impact tests on 3D woven composites with polymer matrix. Coupon specimens are either hold by two square jaws with a circular free zone (diameter 70 mm) or simply supported. Jaws have been chosen to obtain boundary conditions which are easily reproducible in Finite Element simulations. The impactor is hemispheric with a 40 mm diameter, made of steel, and its mass is set to 15 kg. Different energy levels (from 60 J to 210 J) have been achieved by changing the velocity set by adjusting the height of the drop weight. Each test has been repeated two or three times to estimate the scattering. Impact tests have been performed at room temperature.

Figure 1: Falling weight impact testing and jaws with a circular free zone developed at Onera or a simply supported device

2.2 Damages due to impact loading

Some plates have been cut through the damage zone in different directions (0° , 45° , 90°) in order to observe in details the damage mechanisms occurring during impact tests. Microscopic observations have been made on polished faces. They have been completed with the analysis of micro-tomographies on others specimens to have an estimation of the three dimensional localization of the damages within the material. The microscopic observations of the cut faces through the damage zone (Figure 2) show that damages are mainly matrix cracking and debondings between the yarns. The debondings can be quite long but are not continuous and follow the architecture of the material. Most of the matrix cracking is observed between the yarns. The damage zone is approximately conical through the thickness. The back face of the plate is subjected to a local in-plane tensile loading due to the global bending of the plate. It creates straight matrix cracks in this zone. Through the thickness, the plate is subjected to inter-laminar shear stresses, especially at mid thickness. The inter-laminar shear stresses create matrix cracks which are inclined and present a round shape. They also create debondings between yarns since the repartition of the debondings seems to follow the shear stresses one. Finally, no or few damage is observed under the contact zone between the plate and the impactor. This could be explained by the high level of hydrostatic pressure located directly under the impactor. Indeed, the hydrostatic pressure may reinforce the apparent strength of the material and prevent the creation of cracks as already observed for laminate composites [8]. To resume, a diffuse damage is induced by impact and this enables to propose a modelling which applies the principles of diffuse damage mechanics.

Figure 2: Microscopic observation of damages for a 100 J impact test

3 DAMAGE MODELLING

3.1 Onera Damage Model for polymer matrix composites (ODM_PMC)

The Onera Damage Model is a macroscopic model for woven composites with polymer matrix, developed at Onera and based on continuum damage mechanics [9]. ODM-PMC is able to predict the behaviour, damage and failure of such composites submitted to quasi-static and fatigue tensile loadings [10, 11]. The viscous behaviour is described with a spectral formulation [12, 13]. The principle of a spectral formulation is to divide the viscous behaviour into several elementary viscous mechanisms. The high difference between matrix and yarns mechanical properties orientates the damages along the microstructure.

Two kinds of damages are represented with the model. The effects of these damages are taken into

account in the three material directions. A coupling between the different directions of the material is considered as observed during experimental tests. The unilateral aspect of damage is represented through an activation index that activates the effects of the damage in tension only, when cracks are opened. The damage variables are classified through their effect on the behaviour. Matrix cracks have a nonlinear effect on the behaviour whereas yarns failures have a nonlinear and softening effect on the behaviour

The out-of-plane macroscopic damage which corresponds to the inter-yarn debondings appearing under impact loading is also described with the model. This damage has an important effect on the behaviour because of high non linearities occurring under impact.

As mentioned previously, the absence of damage in the area in contact with the impactor, as observed in Figure 2, is assumed to be induced by a strengthening of the apparent resistance of the material in this area which sustains a tri-axial compression state resulting from the hemispherical shape of the impactor. This reinforcing effect of hydrostatic pressure has already been described in laminated composites [8, 14]. So, the influence of the hydrostatic pressure has been considered in the model.

3.2 Identification

This model has been implemented in the *implicit* FE code Abaqus/Standard. Only the circular free zone of the plate is considered and according to symmetries, only one quarter of the system is represented. The impactor is modelled using an isotropic elastic behaviour law. Orthotropic elastic simulations of the plate have shown the necessity to take into account the damage mechanisms in the simulations (black line on the Figure 3). Thus, ODM_PMC has been used to model the behaviour of the plate. The in-plane parameters of the model have already been identified on static tests (tension, creep, etc.) but the through-the-thickness properties are still difficult to identify on simple static tests. Moreover, parametric studies have shown that the through-the-thickness damage, representative of debondings, is the main dissipating energy mode in the model. The through-the-thickness damage properties of ODM_PMC have been identified on the 150J impact test in such a way that the peak force, the dissipated energy and the spread of the damage zones are well described by comparison with experimental data and the microscopic observations (Figure 3).

Figure 3 : Identification of through-the-thickness damage properties on damage pattern and impact force versus time histories at impact energy of 150 J

Then, to validate the identification of the different parameters, different simulations with different impacts energy levels have been lead and comparisons with experimental impact testing have been proposed.

3.3 Prediction of the impact behaviour

The Figure 4 shows that the model is able to correctly describe the impact behaviour for different energy levels (60 J, 100 J, 150 J and 200 J). The time of contact is slightly underestimated but the maximal peak force is well predicted.

Figure 4: Force versus time history at 200 J, 150 J, 100 J and 60 J

3.4 Prediction of damage zones

A comparison between the experimental and predicted damage zones is presented on Figure 5. It is shown that the prediction of matrix cracks distribution presents a typical pattern which is observed experimentally. The impact axis is preserved from matrix damage in both the simulation and test results. However, the extent of the predicted matrix cracks area is slightly greater than what is experimentally observed. Concerning the yarn failures, the introduction of the hydrostatic pressure enables to confine the apparition of failures in compression under the impactor as observed experimentally. Moreover, on the back face of the plate, yarn failures, created under tension, are described with the model according to experimental observations. Finally, the predominant damage mode under impact, the interyarns debondings, is also well represented in the simulations. Some damage is predicted in the axis of impact, which is consistent with experimental observations. The damage pattern presents a characteristic shape for this damage mode. However, as well as for matrix cracks, there is an overestimation of the debondings extent with the model but their magnitudes remain consistent with experimental observations.

Figure 5: Comparison between the estimated damage zones and experimental observations (matrix cracking, yarns fractures and interyarn debondings) at an impact energy level of 100 J

3.5 Prediction of the depth of indentation

The dent is a characteristic sign of impact and the estimation of its depth enables to establish relationships between dent and damage area as it is commonly done for laminates. It is also interesting to establish a relationship between the dent and the incident energy of impact.

In this study, the dent is naturally predicted with ODM_PMC thanks to permanent deformations resulting from the thermal residual stress relaxation in the plane during the mesodamage creation. It is, then, not necessary to introduce a plastic deformation in the model. The depth of the indentation has been numerically determined as the maximal out-of-plane displacement when the impactor is no longer in contact with the plate. The estimated dent can be considered as a permanent dent. Figure 6 illustrates an excellent agreement with the experimental data in the considered energy ranges.

Figure 6: Comparison between the predicted indentation depth and experimental data for different energy levels

All these comparisons between the impact prediction with the model and the experimental results have shown the ability of the model to estimate both global (maximal peak force) and local (distribution and size of damage area) quantities satisfactorily. The efficiency of the model has been proven for the prediction of the permanent dent, so that relationships between impact parameters (incident energy, permanent dent, damage area), usually determined by experiments, can now be numerically estimated.

4 THE POST-IMPACT RESIDUAL STRENGTH ANALYSIS

Damage tolerance in composites is usually studied by determining the effect of different impact energies on the residual strength of the composite. The global testing process in this study has been divided in two steps: in the first, the specimen is subjected to low-energy transverse impact that generates a certain degree of damage inside the specimen; then the damaged specimen is tested in in-plane compression or in-plane tension to determine its residual strength (stiffness and strength). The Compression After Impact (CAI) test is used to be the experimental test of components damaged by low energy impact in laminates. However, Tensile tests After Impact (TAI) have also been made on the material of the present study because 3D woven composites do not exhibit large delaminations

after impact and consequently CAI may not be the most detrimental case to estimate the residual performances. All the specimens have been impacted by using the simply-supported device as shown on Figure 1 and subjected to static tests (tension or compression) on a servo-hydraulic machine. The dimensions of specimens tested in tension and compression differ because of the device capacity.

A two-step simulation approach, as illustrated on

Figure 7, has also been proposed in order to describe the different damages and to predict the residual strength. The first step in the approach is the impact simulation performed using the *implicit* solver Abaqus/standard. The second stage in the approach uses the impact damage state in the numerical model and the same material model for the simulation of the compression or tension behaviour and residual strength. The identification of the model remains unchanged with respect to the simulation of the impact, with the exception of the elastic moduli and the parameters of the regularization method used to describe the softening behaviour induced by yarns failure.

Figure 7: Two-step simulation approach on 3D woven composite.

The important failure modes observed in experiments can be captured with these numerical simulations as shown on Figure 8 and Figure 9 for Compression After Impact (80 J) and Tension After Impact (80 J) respectively.

Comparisons between the predicted and experimental residual strength and stiffness for CAI and TAI are presented on Figure 10 and Figure 11. A large reduction in residual strength (Figure 11) can be observed either in tension and compression after impact. The loss is more important in tension which means that the classical CAI tests are not the most detrimental case to evaluate the residual performance for this material. We also observe two distinct areas. For lower incident energy levels, a moderate loss of resistance is obtained under compression and tension. For larger levels of incident energy, a reversal in the trend is observed. However, it is worth mentioning that the widths of the specimen are not the same in tension and in compression. The specimen in compression is wider than in tension. It would be interesting to experimentally confirm this trend with identical specimens in tension and compression, preferably with larger specimens to be more representative of industrial problems.

Figure 8: Damage evolution (yarn failure) after the CAI simulation at 80 J and failure observed in the coupon.

Figure 9: Damage evolution (yarn failure) after the TAI simulation at 80 J and after the TAI simulation at 80 J and failure observed in the coupon.

Concerning the residual stiffness, the loss under compression is really small since under compression, cracks are closed and there is no delamination. On the contrary, the loss is more important under tension along with the incident energy level.

Figure 10: Effect of low velocity impact on compression stiffness and tension stiffness: comparison between tests and simulation

Figure 11: Effect of low velocity impact on compression strength and tension strength: comparison between tests and simulation

Another point to be noticed is that the nonlinear behavior for TAI is underestimated. In addition to a better in-plane identification of the effects of the yarns failure and debondings, improving the regularization method could increase the non-linearity of the behavior in the simulations to be closer to the experimental nonlinear behavior.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a two-step simulation approach has been proposed and has consisted in predicting the damage induced by an impact in order to estimate the residual strength of the specimen. The same model is used as well for the impact as for the residual performance simulations by using the implicit FE code Abaqus/standard. The results obtained are encouraging. The model already shows interesting predictive capabilities that can allow obtaining trends and performing comparative studies. In addition, it is now possible to numerically estimate the relationships between incident energy, dent depth, damaged area and residual performance.

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